

Chemistry of portland cement[†]

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Manuscript received 19 September 2002

A brief account of the raw materials, fluxes and mineralizers used in the manufacture of portland cement is given. Different cement modules, in terms of oxide composition normally required for its manufacture, are also given. Major chemical reactions involved in the manufacture of portland cement clinker, properties and hydration behavior of the cement have been discussed. Various type of cements which can be derived from portland cement are included in this article.

Cement dates back to antiquity and one can only speculate about its discovery. For the purposes of construction, a material is said to be cement if it has adhesive and cohesive properties and is capable of binding together mineral fragments so as to produce a continuous, compact mass of masonry. There are a large number of cementing materials which are being used for this purpose, including the hydraulic cements, lime, gypsum plasters etc. On October 21, 1824, an English man Joseph Aspdin¹, a Leeds builder, took out a patent for making artificial cement, he called his product portland cement because concrete made from it resembled a famous building stone obtained from the Isle of Portland near England. Aspdin's early cement was nothing more than a hydraulic lime, nevertheless it was an essential link in the development of portland cement industry as we know it today.

When calcareous materials (lime bearing substances such as limestone) is intimately mixed with argillaceous materials (SiO_2 , Al_2O_3 , Fe_2O_3 etc. bearing substances such as clay) and burned at a high temperature, portland cement clinker is formed. This on grinding with gypsum (act as set regulator) into fine powder gives portland cement. When water is added, it sets and hardens and is known as hydraulic cement. A number of text books have been published which deal with various aspects of cement chemistry²⁻⁴. In addition to the text books and research journals, different aspects of cement chemistry are being discussed in International Congress on Chemistry of Cements, being held after every six years^{5,6}.

Raw materials for the manufacture of portland cement

Minerals of natural origin as well as industrial products

can be used for the production of cement⁷. Starting materials for this purpose are mineral compounds containing the main components of cement : lime, silica, alumina and iron oxide. Required proportions of these compounds are seldom found in only one raw material. Therefore, it is usually necessary to select a measured mixture of a high lime component, i.e. calcareous materials (limestone – mainly CaCO_3) with argillaceous materials (clay component – $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot n\text{SiO}_2 \cdot x\text{H}_2\text{O}$) which is lower in lime, containing however more silica, alumina and iron oxide.

Corrective ingredients :

If an essential chemical component needed in the cement raw mixture is not present in the required amount, appropriate ingredients are used as additives. For meeting the deficiency of silica in the raw mix, sand, high silica clay, diatomite etc. are used as additives. Iron oxide present in the raw mix enhances the clinkerization reaction by increasing the molten phase. Its deficiency can be removed by adding pyrite cinders, iron ores etc. in an appropriate amount.

Fuel :

In order to remove moisture, decompose carbonates, and sintering of the oxides, the mixture of the raw materials are heated with suitable fuels. On a cost basis, coal is frequently preferred to either natural gas or oil, although coal ash usually has too high an iron content. A number of wastes have also been examined as supplementary fuels. Colliery waste (mine stone), oil shales, household refuse, used and rejected tyres and sewage sludge have also been used. Coke has been ground with raw materials to improve the thermal efficiency of a dry process by allowing it to burn in the later stages of

[†]Dedicated to Professor R. P. Rastogi.

a dry process kiln pre heater and may also be used as a partial substitute for coal in the kiln flame.

Gypsum :

Gypsum is incorporated into portland cement clinker to regulate setting speed, i.e. to act as a set retarder. It is added to the clinker during grinding. The level is determined by the sulfate content of the clinker and that required in the finished cement, i.e. a total sulfate content, expressed as SO₃ is generally in the range 2–5% for ordinary portland cement. The amount of gypsum is expressed as SO₃ because CaO of gypsum (CaO.SO₃.2H₂O) is expressed separately with the total amount of CaO.

Cement modules :

For a long time portland cement was manufactured on the basis of practical experience collected from the process of production. When comparing chemical analyses of portland cement, it was found that certain relations exist between the percentages (weight percent) of lime on the one hand and the combination of silica, alumina and iron oxide on the other. Later this oxide ratio gave rise to the formation of the so called cement modules as given below⁷ :

(i) Hydraulic modules (HM),

$$HM = \frac{CaO}{SiO_2 + Al_2O_3 + Fe_2O_3} = 1.7-2.3$$

(ii) Silica ratio (SR),

$$SR = \frac{SiO_2}{Al_2O_3 + Fe_2O_3} = 1.9-3.2$$

(iii) Silicic acid ratio (SAR),

$$SAR = \frac{SiO_2}{Al_2O_3} = 2.5-3.5$$

(iv) Alumina ratio (AR),

$$AR = \frac{Al_2O_3}{Fe_2O_3} = 1.5-2.5$$

(v) Lime saturation factor (LSF),

$$LSF = \frac{CaO - 0.7 SO_3}{2.8 SiO_2 + 1.2 Al_2O_3 + 0.65 Fe_2O_3} \\ = \leq 1.2 \geq 0.66$$

Manufacture of ordinary portland cement (OPC)

The commonly used portland cement is known as ordinary portland cement (OPC). The manufacture of this type of cement started in a vertical shaft kiln (VSK) in a

crude form as used by Aspdin. However, now-a-days it is mostly manufactured in large capacity energy efficient rotary kilns. The increasing prices for energy and the regulations of the cement industry with respect to the environmental protection have been the driving force for the developments towards more energy efficient cement plants. The various unit operations in the process of manufacture starts with the crushing stage, where big size of raw materials are crushed to smaller sizes. Then follows a stage called raw grinding where the various raw materials in suitable proportions are ground to a fine powder. After this follows the stage of blending and homogenization which reduces the variations and ensures optimum particle size distribution. The mixing and grinding of the raw materials can be done either in water or in a dry condition; hence the name wet and dry processes. Now the advanced cement plants use only dry process. After this the kiln feed is heated to a temperature around 1400–1500° (in the burning zone of the kiln) where decomposition of CaCO₃ (calcination), agglomeration and formation of nodules of the calcined kiln feed occurs and as a result, cementitious compounds are formed and are known as *clinker*. The clinker needs rapid cooling in coolers to ensure good quality. At the last stage the clinker after aeration is mixed with a small amount of gypsum (2–5%) and ground to a fine powder called cement.

Symbols for oxides and mineral phases :

A special shorthand symbols are used by the cement chemists to simplify the formulae :

Oxide	CaO	SiO ₂	Al ₂ O ₃	Fe ₂ O ₃	H ₂ O	Na ₂ O	K ₂ O
Symbol	C	S	A	F	H	N	K

Other symbols such as \bar{S} for SO₃ (sulfuric anhydrite) exists but are less often used. The abbreviated symbols for mineral phases are given in the Table 1.

Table 1. Main components of portland cement

Name of compound	Oxide composition	Abbreviation	Composition wt. %
Tricalcium silicate	Ca ₃ SiO ₅	C ₃ S	30–55
Dicalcium silicate	Ca ₂ SiO ₄	β -C ₂ S	20–50
Tricalcium aluminate	Ca ₃ Al ₂ O ₆	C ₃ A	7–12
Tetra-calcium aluminoferrite	4 CaO.Al ₂ O ₃ .Fe ₂ O ₃	C ₄ AF	6–11

Reactions in clinker formation :

Limestone and clay are intimately mixed and heated, ultimately to a temperature of about 1500° for the manufacture of portland cement clinker. Following major reactions occur. (a) Below 1300°, decomposition of limestone and

clay leading to the formation of lime, SiO_2 , Al_2O_3 and Fe_2O_3 occur. These oxides then react to form belite (C_2S), aluminate (C_3A) and ferrite (C_4AF). A small amount of molten liquid is formed at this stage which has an important effect in promoting the reaction. (b) Clinkerization reactions take place between 1300 and 1500°. At 1500°, about 20–30% melt is formed mainly from the aluminate and ferrite. At this temperature much of the belite reacts with free lime to form alite (C_3S). The material nodulizes, to form the clinker.

Fluxes and mineralizers :

The fluxes are generally considered as an agent that promotes a reaction by increasing the quantity of melt at a given temperature during clinkerization. In commercial portland cement clinker burning, the presence of Al_2O_3 and Fe_2O_3 in the raw material acts as flux⁸. Mineralizers are substances which through some mechanism, accelerate the rate of the reaction between solid phases, or in the molten state or at the melt – solid interface.

Amongst the known mineralizers and fluxes, calcium fluoride (fluorspar CaF_2) has been extensively used. Other fluosilicates and fluorides are also very effective. When fluorides are added, the process of clinkerizations is enhanced and the effect increases with increasing fluoride additions. However, the fluoride has detrimental effect on the properties of cement.

Composition :

In reality, the silicates in cement are not pure compounds, but minor oxides are there in the form of solid solution. The tricalcium silicate and dicalcium silicate phases in cement are called alite and belite, respectively. The calculation of the potential compositions of the portland cement is done by Bogue⁹ equation,

$$\text{C}_3\text{S} = 4.07 \text{CaO} - 7.60 \text{SiO}_2 - 6.72 \text{Al}_2\text{O}_3 - 1.43 \text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3 - 2.85 \text{SO}_3$$

$$\text{C}_2\text{S} = 2.85 \text{SiO}_2 - 0.75 \text{C}_3\text{S}$$

$$\text{C}_3\text{A} = 2.65 \text{Al}_2\text{O}_3 - 1.65 \text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3$$

$$\text{C}_4\text{AF} = 3.04 \text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3$$

A general idea about the oxide composition of the cement is given in Table 2 and that of mineral phases are given in Table 1.

In addition to the oxides listed, there exist minor compounds such as MgO , TiO_2 , Mn_2O_3 etc. They usually amount to not more than a few percent of the mass of the cement.

Table 2. Usual composition limits of portland cement

Oxide	Content %
CaO	60–67
SiO_2	17–25
Al_2O_3	3–8
Fe_2O_3	0.5–0.6
MgO	0.5–4.0
Alkalis ($\text{Na}_2\text{O} + \text{K}_2\text{O}$)	0.3–1.2
SO_3 (as sulfate)	2.0–3.5
Loss on ignition (LOI)	2
Insoluble residue (IR)	0.5

Analysis of the cement

The composition of the cement is generally determined by chemical method¹⁰. The metal ions are estimated either gravimetrically, titrimetrically or colourimetrically. From the amount of metal ions, the corresponding amount of oxides is calculated and then from Bogue equation, the mineral phases are estimated.

From atomic absorption spectrometer the metal ions are estimated¹¹ and the mineral phases are calculated from Bogue equation. X-Ray fluorescence spectrometric technique gives a direct estimation of the oxide and mineral phases of the cement by comparison with a known standard.

Optical microscopic method and X-ray diffraction technique¹¹ also give information about different mineral phases of the cement.

Properties of cement

Setting and hardening, compressive strength, soundness, fineness, water-cement ratio, heat of hydration etc. are some of the main properties of the cement.

Setting : Stiffening of the cement paste after addition of water is called setting. It depends on a number of factors such as : (i) percentage of the clinker present, mainly C_3A , (ii) percent of gypsum ground with the clinker, (iii) particle size of solids, (iv) ratio of water-to-cement, (v) temperature, (vi) presence of alkalis. Hardening starts soon after initial stiffening and is mainly due to the hydration of the silicate phases, where crystalline $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ and calcium silicate hydrates (C-S-H) are formed.

Compressive strength : Portland cement is a product which gives good compressive strength both at the early and late stages. Hydration of C_3S is responsible for early strengths while C_2S hydration at later strengths.

Soundness : Cement is considered sound if it does not

expand on hydration. Free lime (CaO_f) and free magnesia (MgO_f) are responsible for soundness in cement. The manufacturers have to control the burning process such that minimum quantity of CaO_f or MgO_f is formed in the clinker.

Fineness : The specific surface per unit area is important for a powdery material like cement. Usually rate of reaction is proportional to the surface area and hence finer the cement better the quality.

Water-cement ratio : The amount of water required to form a paste of standard consistency is known as the water-cement ratio (w/c) which is generally 0.5. Lower the ratio required, better the quality of the cement.

Heat of hydration : The heat evolved during the hydration has an important role to play especially when mass concreting is done as in the construction of dams. Higher heat of hydration may lead to cracks in massive structures like dams.

In addition to the above mentioned properties, cements should not have more than 0.6% alkalis ($\text{Na}_2\text{O} + \text{K}_2\text{O}$) as it has been found that alkalis react with some reactive aggregates in the concrete causing cracks due to expansion called the alkali – aggregate reaction. Similarly, higher doses of chloride (>0.05%) have been found to create corrosion in Reinforced Cement Concrete (RCC) and resulting in failure of the concrete.

Hydration and setting process

In cement chemistry one has to differentiate between setting and hydration¹². Hydration refers to the chemical reaction between cement and water while setting concerns the early formation of the three-dimensional network and the first increase of the concrete strength.

In fact, hydration is not setting, indeed both may be independently observed. For example, the chemical transformation of anhydrous binder into hydrates occurs as soon as it is mixed with water. However, if excess water is added to the cement, making it a suspension which is dispersed by stirring in order to prevent contacts between particles, the setting does not occur. Thus, the hydrate formation is not a sufficient condition of setting. The setting can occur only when water/cement ratio is low enough to form a paste of standard consistency, and the hydrates formed have compact structures.

The mechanism of hardening of cement is a very complex process. Historically Le Chatelier considered that cement hydration occurred by the dissolution of anhydrous phases followed by the crystallization of the hydrates in the

interlocking mass. Michaelis on the other hand thought that the solidification of a paste occurred by the formation of a colloidal material which hardened as it lost water. This lost water further hydrated the anhydrous cement. However, according to current view, the process of hardening can be visualized as follows.

When water is added to portland cement, exothermic complex reactions occur. As a result of this cement sets and hardens. The development of strength of a cement paste is associated with the precipitation of hydration products of very low solubility to form a cohesive matrix binding the residual cement grains into a composite solid. The main source of strength is derived from the hydration of two principal silicate phases, i.e. alite and belite. The aluminate phase (both C_3A and C_4AF) because of rapid hydration, influences the setting but do not contribute significantly to the final strength of the paste. Gypsum in portland cement controls the flash set (the reaction of C_3A with water is very violent and leads to immediate stiffening of the paste, known as flash set) that might otherwise result from the rapid formation of the calcium aluminate hydrates.

Hydration of portland cement :

The chemistry of cement hydration is a very complex phenomenon. This is mainly due to a large number of variables like crystalline structure of reactive phases, fineness, thermal history, temperature, water-cement ratio etc. It is therefore difficult to study the hydration mechanism as a whole but study of the hydration of individual phases can give some information of the overall hydration and it has been discussed briefly by Potgieter and Kaspar¹³.

Hydration of tricalcium and dicalcium silicate :

Tricalcium silicate, C_3S (alite) and dicalcium silicate, $\beta\text{-C}_2\text{S}$ (the dominant form of belite), reacting independently with water yield the same products, namely, calcium hydroxide and calcium silicate hydrates ($\text{Ca}_3\text{Si}_2\text{O}_5$ normally written as C–S–H gels)¹⁴. Although both the silicates hydrate in a similar way, the hydration of C_3S is exothermic and much faster than that of C_2S . The following equations¹⁵ may be used to describe the hydration reaction

The above equations are over simplified. C_3S produces three times as much $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ as C_2S . Calcium silicate hydrates (C–S–H) comprise a range of phases of differing composition and Ca : Si ratio depending on factors such as time, temperature and water-cement ratio¹⁶. Because of higher

hydration rate, the alite phase contributes to the early strength development. On the other hand, belite phase hydrates^{17,18} with much slower speed and is responsible for the later age (14–28 days) strength in the hydrated cement.

Hydration of tricalcium aluminate (C_3A) :

C_3A in portland cement, although in lower proportions than the silicate phases, is of great importance owing to its high reactivity with water during the early stages of hydration. Because of its high reactivity, its reaction rate is controlled to avoid flash set by adding gypsum. Hydration reactions have been discussed by Brown¹⁹. When water is added to C_3A , the following reactions take place,

When lime is present, in the absence of gypsum, C_4AH_{13} is formed and is stabilized at ambient temperature by the high lime environment. This reaction is the principal cause of flash set in portland cements,

When gypsum ($CaSO_4 \cdot 2H_2O$) is added to the cement clinker, ettringite ($C_3A \cdot 3CaSO_4 \cdot 32H_2O$) is formed, which controls the setting behavior of the cement. Following reaction takes place :

When the amount of calcium sulfate is not sufficient to convert all the C_3A into ettringite, the free C_3A reacts with ettringite forming monosulfoaluminate hydrate ($C_3A \cdot CaSO_4 \cdot 12H_2O$). Further, when sulfate ion in solution is decreased below a detectable limit, calcium monosulfoaluminate hydrate decomposes.

Hydration of calcium aluminoferrite (C_4AF) :

Calcium aluminoferrite is actually a solid solution within the C_2A – C_2F systems and the compositions in ordinary portland cement approximates to C_4AF . The hydration of the ferrite phase is very similar to that of C_3A both in the presence and absence of sulfate. However, the rate of hydration is much lower than the C_3A and reactivity increases with increasing A/F ratio. The hydration reactions can be expressed as

Portland cement hydration :

Hydration of cement is an exothermic process. The rate

Fig. 1. Rate of heat evolution during the hydration of portland cement.

of heat evolution with hydration time is given in Fig. 1. As the cement comes in contact to water, a rapid heat evolution takes place (peak I) mainly due to the hydration of aluminate phase. The duration of this high rate of hydration is very short, and there follows a so-called dormant period, also known as induction period, during which the rate is very low. This period lasts from one to two hours during which the cement paste is workable. During this period the hydration products cover the anhydrous cement and do not allow further reaction. But after certain time, rupturing of the hydration products takes place and as a result water molecules reach the fresh surface of cement and the hydration accelerates with time and reaches to maximum at about 10 h (peak II). During this period mainly hydration of C_3S phase occurs. When large amount of hydration products are formed, the hydration decreases and becomes diffusion-controlled. In some of the cement, third peak (peak III) appears at about 30 h due to renewed hydration of C_3A phase.

A summarized scheme of hydration in terms of hydration products has been proposed by Double²⁰ and is shown in Fig. 2. The reactions shown do not occur independently.

Fig. 2. Schematic representation of the anhydrous constituents in portland cement clinker and the products formed during hydration. The areas of the 'boxes' give the approximate volume proportions of the phases.

During hydration, there is an increase in the volume of solids and this is accompanied by the growth of the hydrates

into the water-filled spaces in the cement microstructure during the hardening process. The most common hydration products are $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$, C-S-H, ettringite, monosulfate, different AF_m phases etc. The amount and the crystallinity depends on the composition of cements.

Portland cement derivatives

Various attempts have been made to improve the quality of ordinary portland cement but the intrinsic disadvantages of portland cement with respect to its stiffness, tensile strength, fracture toughness and creep properties could not be overcome in any substantial manner. Hence, researchers continued their efforts in developing various derivatives of portland cement. As a result, a host of derived formulations are produced and marketed all over the world.

Rapid hardening portland cement (RHPC) :

OPC with relatively more C_3S (50–65%) and higher surface area (325–500 m^2/kg Blain) is known as RHPC. The C_3A content is also kept a little high (8–12%). It sets quickly and gives high early strength. It is used in precast concretes, quick release of moulds, repair works and speedy construction.

Extra rapid-hardening portland cement (ExRHPC) :

In this cement ~ 2% CaCl_2 is added during the grinding of clinker with gypsum. This is used for emergency repairs.

Sulfate resisting portland cement (SRC) :

This cement is produced to make concrete which has resistance to destructive attack by sulfates. Formation of ettringite within an already hardened concrete structure by the ingress of SO_4^{2-} ions and water results in expansive forces which are ultimately capable of cracking and severely weakening the structure. Sulfate-resisting portland cements are designated to overcome this problem by burning the calcareous and argillaceous raw materials with iron oxide, and sometimes sand as well to give a satisfactory silica ratio. In these cements C_3A is less than 3% and the ferrite phase is not only C_4AF but lies within the range $\text{C}_4\text{AF}-\text{C}_6\text{AF}_2$. During hydration less ettringite is found at early stages. It is used in shipyard and foundation in coastal areas.

Low heat portland cement (LHPC) :

For large dam construction and also for massive support columns and supporting walls, which require vast quantities of concrete, regular portland cement can hardly be applied due to the generation of heat of hydration. It is an ordinary portland cement with low C_3A and C_3S content. In this cement C_2S content is high and sometimes this cement is also known as belite cement.

Oil-well cement (OWC) :

Oil-well cements are used by the petroleum industry to prevent water into the borehole for crude oil exploration. Oil-well cements are based on ordinary portland cement with low MgO and C_3A and high C_3S content. These cements are used in the form of slurry and hence some additives are added which can maintain stable fluidity and high temperature and pressures prevailing in the wells. Such cements are also expected to give strength within short period once the slurry reaches the application point. It is also expected that the strength should be retained, in spite of the presence of corrosive agents such as sulfates and chlorides in the subsoil environment. The total time in which the cement slurry has to be prepared, applied and allowed to gain strength, varies from two to four hours.

White portland cement (WPC) :

It is ordinary portland cement with low content of C_4AF (max 0.4% Fe_2O_3) and alkalis ($\text{Na}_2\text{O} + \text{K}_2\text{O}$). It is made from raw materials containing very little iron oxide and manganese oxide. China clay is generally used, together with chalk or limestone, free from specified impurities. Oil is used as fuel for the kiln in order to avoid contamination by coal ash. Because of the lack of sufficient iron-containing material, which normally acts as a flux during burning, combination of the raw material is more difficult. Higher burning temperatures than usual (1550–1600°) are often necessary to achieve clinkering. This is mainly used for architectural purpose and decorative work.

Coloured portland cement (CPC) :

The base cement is white or ordinary portland cement with nearly 10% pigments. The colours are blue, yellow, green, red, black etc. The pigments are inert but may slightly reduce the cementing power. Their uses are decorative like white portland cement.

Water-repellant and hydrophobic portland cement (HPC) :

As the name implies, hydrophobic cement means water-hating. It is obtained by grinding ordinary portland cement clinker with an additive like sodium oleate, calcium stearate etc. (0.1–0.5%) by wt. of clinker. Such cement can be transported even in rainy season without any damage to its hydraulic property. The water-repellant property can be destroyed by grinding such cement in a concrete mixer, where the hydraulic coating is removed and then it works as ordinary portland cement. It can be used for longer periods in extremely wet climatic conditions.

Masonry cement (MPC) :

Masonry cements are composed of portland cement, an

inert filler such as slag or limestone and a small quantity of plasticizer. The compressive strength of this cement for 7 and 28 days shall not be less than 25 and 50 kg/cm², respectively. This cement is used for low-cost housing.

Expansive cement (ExPC) :

Expansive cements are ordinary portland cements mixed with C₃AS phase. They expand slightly during the first few days of hydration and can be used to compensate for the effects of shrinkage in normal portland cements and concretes.

Portland slag cement (PSC) :

Portland blast furnace slag cements consist of portland cement containing granulated blast furnace slag (25–65%). The granulated slag does not set in water, but in the presence of activators like lime, alkalis and portland cement, shows hydraulic properties. It has lower heat of hydration than ordinary portland cement. The concrete made with PSC has better durability and resistance to sulfate and chloride attack.

Portland pozzolanic cement (PPC) :

Portland pozzolanic cements are portland cements containing natural or artificial pozzolanas. Pozzolana is a silicious and aluminous material which in itself possess little or no cementitious property but combine with calcium hydroxide in the presence of water at ordinary temperature to form substances which possess cementing properties. Natural pozzolanas include volcanic tuffs, zeolites, reactive form of hydrated silica like diatomite etc. and artificial pozzolanas include pulverized fuel ash (PFA), fly ash, rice husk ash etc. Natural pozzolanas generally contain 60–85% amorphous SiO₂. When pozzolanic materials in an appropriate amounts are added to cement, they react with calcium hydroxide formed during the hydration of cement, forming additional calcium silicate hydrate. The pozzolanic reaction occurs as

The pozzolanic reaction is slow, so the rate of strength development and the heat of hydration associated with this reaction are also low. It utilizes waste materials and thus has low production cost. It has good long-term strength and better durability.

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